

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ASONG****FIRST NAME: ABELT LEKE****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author used Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 9%

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 5-7 critical concepts with the page number in the text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Writing a Good Essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 6-14)
2. Punctuations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 15-23)
3. American vs British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 33-39)
5. Style guide (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 40-42)
6. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 58-64)

ACADEMIC AND PROFESSIONAL WRITING

1. INTRODUCTION

Individuals who do not have English as their first language have significant hurdles in academic writing. English is complex, and it is difficult to understand all the guidelines required to communicate effectively across different audiences. I completed my Master's program in development studies and diplomacy with a solid understanding of academic writing. As a doctoral student, mastering the art of effective communication in English is a central focus of my academic career. This is a significant milestone in my professional career trajectory, which will enhance my skills as a non-native English writer to apply the concepts of academic writing, as taught in this course. This response paper explores linguistic ways to improve communication when interacting with diverse audiences. For individuals who are not native English speakers like myself, it is essential to understand these qualities to effectively and concisely communicate ideas. The course pack focuses on the structural and stylistic elements of creating professional works that adhere to international standards. By applying the principles of clear exposition, logical

argumentation, and appropriate language use, I aim to improve my academic writing skills. Strengthening my academic writing skills will improve my communication ability with more significant consideration of every aspect of English writing guidelines. As I delve into this course, I am confident that I will receive support from my professor and colleagues who, regardless of their backgrounds, bring a wealth of experience to this course. The paper covers five main topics: **Writing a good academic essay, punctuation, American versus British English writing, plagiarism, writing style, and Latin abbreviations and expressions.**

2. WRITING A GOOD ESSAY

Chapter 1 of this course pack, period one, covers the different types of essays and guides for initiating an essay, conducting research on a topic, structuring thoughts, citing sources, and editing. Writing an essay requires careful planning and implementation. Understanding the thesis of a paper ensures that I am aware of the topic that my research will tackle and the methodology employed to express ideas.

Starting an essay is the most challenging part of academic writing because uncertainty about how to approach the topic and structure the essay can make it difficult to start. Furthermore, striving for perfection in the first sentence or paragraph can lead to overthinking about a topic and difficulty starting. The course pack unravels this anxiety and outlines fundamental essay writing guidelines. As stated by Cleenewerck and Gulma (2024, 7), “One of the initial things required for writing is to have enough time to read, research the topic, think, and write. It is never advisable to procrastinate.” When writing a paper, I prefer to start far in advance since it allows me ample time to process my ideas better without feeling pressured to meet the deadline. This approach has proven beneficial to me during my prior academic endeavors. I have produced high-quality essays by employing effective techniques such as brainstorming and outlining, beginning with a preliminary draft to overcome the challenges of initiating an essay.

Moreover, I formulate a coherent framework for my essay, organizing my thoughts systematically and starting with introductions, followed by body paragraphs and a conclusion, contributing to a persuasive essay. Conducting thorough research on a topic is crucial for gathering relevant information to bolster an argument while writing a high-quality essay. I must rely on reputable sources such as scholarly journals, books, and credible websites to substantiate my points. Research backs up arguments by providing relevant evidence, examples, and quotes from credible sources. Research is beneficial, and dedicating time to read this section of the course pack, which gives a brief overview of research, was essential for me to reflect on my approach to writing this paper. The knowledge gained helped me to reflect on my understanding of the chosen topics for discussion. Sources like JSTOR offer valuable resources on scholarly articles, academic journals, and books pertinent to the discussion topic. Additional tools, such as Zotero, are excellent for consolidating material in a single spot and facilitating quick retrieval of references.

The aspect of this course pack I find valuable is the inclusion of a comprehensive discussion on correctly referencing information provided by an author. Citing sources is essential for acknowledging the writer of a book, article, or journal. Mastering referencing requires familiarity with the preferred citation format “of the faculty, school, or journal” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 11). Strengthening my argument with relevant evidence, examples, and quotes from credible sources improves effective communication according to international standards. Having a preference for clear and precise communication by avoiding superfluous jargon and wordiness is the recommended strategy for professional writing.

The process of editing in research is a crucial and pivotal step that ensures clarity, consistency, and overall quality of research. A helpful practice in the editing process is to edit the content of a research paper a few days after it has been written. As a non-native English speaker, I need more time to edit my documents. Hence, it is advisable to follow the recommendation in the course pack that states, “an essay is often recommended to be kept aside for a few days before editing” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 11). Reviewing an essay a couple of days after writing is crucial to consider while editing a research paper. I find it helpful to set aside my essay for a day or two after completing it; this allows for the possibility of fresh ideas that may require a review of the overall structure of my paper to ensure it is logically coherent.

3. PUNCTUATIONS

The art of writing encapsulates the ability to communicate clearly and use punctuation to separate sentences and their elements. When I am reading a sentence, I like to pause, emphasize certain parts of a sentence, and reorganize the structure of the language. This topic from the course pack focuses on communion punctuation marks, which include periods, commas, semicolons, colons, quotation marks, apostrophes, exclamation points, and question marks, among others. According to Gorlewski and Heveron-Smith (2012, 102), “Punctuation can be a creative choice, and the more we know about it, the more fully we can express ourselves.” The author is referring to the idea that using punctuation marks in writing can go beyond merely indicating grammatical structure and serve as a deliberate stylistic or artistic decision made by the author. Instead of following strict rules, the author can create ambiguity, tension, or rhythm in a sentence. For example, exclamation points can add emphasis or drama to a passage. Therefore, punctuation offers the writer a tool for expression and creativity.

Also, what I find intriguing about the information presented in this course material is how singular nouns and plurals are essential in sentence structure. When an “S” in a word is used after a singular noun, it indicates possession or ownership, for example, Peter’s car and John’s book. These two examples refer to Peter owning a car and John owning a book. In other words, the car belongs to Peter, and the book belongs to John. Furthermore, “s” can also be a contraction of “is” or “has.” For example, she’s going to the store (She is going to the store), he’s finished his homework (he has finished his homework), she’s sick (she is sick). Using “s” is interesting because understanding a sentence’s context is crucial in determining whether “s” signifies possession or contraction.

“S” in a word may also indicate plural or singular. It is added to nouns to refer to more than one of something. For example, “dog” could become “dogs,” meaning many dogs. I am surprised that verb conjugation changes its forms depending on the subject tense of the sentence. The third-person singular form of most verbs in the present tense adds an “s.” For example, she walks to school (Third person singular form of the verb “Walk”).

4. AMERICA VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

Deciding whether to write in American or British English is the first time in my academic journey that it is a requirement in a course. I am originally from the Republic of Cameroon, which Britain and France colonized. Southern Cameroon was a former British colony, and since then, the English part of Cameroon has adopted an Anglo-Saxon education system. The course material explains the difference between American and British English in spelling, vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar. American English tends to simplify spellings compared to British English, for example, Color (American) Versus colour (British), Center (American), and Centre (British). I had used these words interchangeably in writing without paying attention to the different spellings. American English is favored compared to British English due to population size, wealth, magnitude of high education, number of publishing industries, and more. Cleenewerck and Gulma (2024, 25) state, “American English has grown steadily in international significance since World War II, parallel to the growth of U.S. political, economic, technological, and cultural influence worldwide.” This statement implies that American English is popular because of America’s significant global influence. English is indeed one of the most widely spoken languages in the world, but most of those who speak English are non-native speakers partly influenced by colonization. According to Sen (2009, 116), “The Introduction of English into the complex hierarchical language system of India has proved the most enduring aspect of this domination.” In other words, the enduring aspect of British rule in India lies in integrating English into the intricate hierarchical language structure. India is the world’s most English-language-spoken country due to colonialism. The marginalization of the mother tongue languages of many countries remains shocking. For example, in the English-speaking part of Cameroon, people continue to use English as the official language, although more than 250 native languages are spoken in the region.

What I find interesting in American and British English is that despite their differences, both languages generally understand it easily. The vocabulary adopted words and phrases from various languages and cultures. For example, Sidewalk (American) and pavement (British), Dining room (American) and Parlour (British). I am a Canadian Citizen and often find that when I use British English words like parlour or touch, the reaction from a Canadian would be, “Sorry, could you repeat what you said?”. This reaction does not mean that they do not know the meaning of the words I have used, but they are not used to communicating in English with British English words. Canadians use the American English words to speak. I want to illustrate that it is vital to be aware of and adhere to the conventions of the targeted audience’s dialect.

While the basic grammar rules are essentially the same, there are subtle differences in usage. Both use punctuation similarly. British English tends to favor single quotation

marks (‘) and American English uses (“). There are instances where British and American English use different prepositions for the same context. For example, “at the weekend” (British) vs “on the weekend” (American). British English often retains more formality and traditional structure compared to American English. Both languages have unique idioms and expressions that may always be understood. For example, “Knock up” (British) versus “to impregnate (American).

I learned that while American English has a significant global influence, it may not be accurate to categorize it as the “dominant language” in the world. English is a widely spoken language, and the official or primary language of many countries, including Canada, Australia, America, New Zealand, and many others, is English. English has become the lingua franca of international communication, business, science, technology, and popular culture.

5. PLAGIARISM

According to Cleenerck and Gulma (2024, 34), “Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of the source of information.” It is an academic offense to use an author’s source of information without crediting the author. The information published by various authors stems from extensive research. The purpose of research is multifaceted and can vary depending on the field, discipline, and specific goals of the researcher. Some common reasons for research include advancing knowledge, solving problems, testing hypotheses, informing decision-making, and enhancing practice. Therefore, I should give researchers credit when writing published or stated information. It is easy to copy and paste information from various sources to write an essay, but I am afraid that is incorrect. The problem of plagiarism can be addressed in multiple ways, including quotes, paraphrasing, technology, and cultural change.

In preparation for this course, I familiarized myself with the rules of plagiarism. I downloaded tools like Zotero to ensure that any information from an article, journal, or book is adequately cited to avoid plagiarizing. I also used Grammarly to check how often I use other sources to write this paper. This assignment aims to learn how to use critical thinking in academic writing and not copy information from different sources to complete the assignment. Three primary citations are highlighted in the course pack: in-text citations, paraphrases, and quotations. Also, it includes different citation styles and standardized formats used to acknowledge and reference sources of information in academic and research writing. Various disciplines and academic institutions may prefer specific citation styles, each with its own rules and guidelines. Some common citations include APA (American Psychological Association), MLA (Modern Language Association), Chicago Manual of Style, and AMA (American Medical Association). These are a few examples of citation styles commonly used in academic writing. Plagiarism is wrong and unethical to use other academic work and claim ownership without proper citation. The most common citation I have used in the past is APA format to write academic papers.

Technology plays a significant role in both facilitating and making it possible to avoid plagiarism. For example, the internet provides easy access to much information, making it tempting for individuals to copy and paste content without proper attribution.

Websites, online databases, and digital libraries make finding and downloading information and academic work that can be plagiarized easily. On the other hand, tools like Grammarly are formidable tools for avoiding plagiarism. What I find important in this course material is that it provides examples of tools that can be used to check and avoid plagiarism. Academic institutions like EUCLID University have strict policies and consequences for academic dishonesty, including plagiarism, to discourage students from engaging in unethical behavior.

6. STYLE GUIDE

Academic writing requires adherence to style guides or manuals to ensure consistency, clarity, and professionalism. Before writing this response paper, I reviewed EUCLID University's preferred style guide. In addition to the guidelines, EUCLID provided a template to ensure students conformed to the writing style guide. Style guides are essential to me because they are used to communicate in various contexts, including publishing, journalism, corporate communications, and academic writing. According to Herman and Redfield (1989, 898), "...Only by developing a language of one's own, only by resisting the temptation to use ready-made language and thus ready-made concepts, can one engage in vigorous and effective thinking in the strictest sense." Writing is an art that requires critical thinking to structure ideas and communicate effectively with people. The course pack has helped me understand that two writing styles are recommended for professional and academic writing: American English writing and British English writing. For years, I have never paid attention to these writing styles. Using grammar, punctuation marks, and sentence structure when writing American or British English is crucial to follow a standard English writing style. Communication cuts across spectrums of audiences worldwide, emphasizing the importance of globalization and how to interact with people using an approach that makes it easy for clarity of expression, respect for one another, and protection of intellectual property rights. Information on copyright laws and other legal and ethical considerations relevant to writing and publishing ensures consistency in writing with the organization's brand.

Writing style constantly evolves, and style guides can vary widely depending on the context and purpose for which they are created. Style guides are invaluable for writers, editors, and communicators, providing clear and consistent guidelines to ensure high-quality writing and communication.

7. LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

Latin is an ancient Indo-European language that the Romans spoke in the classical period of the Roman Empire. It is the official language of the Roman Republic and the Roman Empire. It continues to be used as a lingua franca in various forms across Europe for centuries after the fall of the Western Roman Empire. Latin has significantly influenced many modern languages, particularly those of the Romance language family (such as Italian, Spanish, French, Portuguese, and Romanian), as well as English, due to its

widespread use in scholarly, religious, and legal contexts throughout history. Latin is used for business, formal, and technical writing. Abbreviations in Latin are commonly used, especially in inscriptions, manuscripts, and official documents. I never paid attention to Latin abbreviations in English writing because I became so used to them that they started sounding like common words used in writing English. Latin is often used for specialized terminology and phrases, particularly in law, medicine, biology, and theology. They are also used in quotations or citations from ancient texts or classical authors, for example, etc. (and so on), et al. (and other people), i.e., (that is), N.B. (nota bene). Overall, Latin plays a significant role in academic writing, providing precision, tradition, and a connection to classical scholarship and intellectual heritage. However, its usage may vary depending on the field of study, the author's preferences, and the academic community's conventions.

8. CONCLUSION

For Non-native English speakers like myself, I am confident that by the end of this course, my writing skills will significantly increase. The explicit and detail-oriented course pack provides a baseline for my doctorate academic journey. Building on my prior knowledge of academic writing can only improve. English is complex and has firm rules that make academic writing coherent and improve clarity in communication. In addition, colonization played a significant role in shaping how English is communicated worldwide. For this Ph.D. program, I will focus on using American English and enhancing my professional writing skills.

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